

Single-nanoparticle gate-sensitive STM spectroscopy

Deliverable 4.1 concerns the scanning tunneling spectroscopy of a single quantum dot (nanoparticle, molecule) in the presence of a nearby gate potential, allowing for electrostatically tuning in situ the dot chemical potential. This project requires realizing a surface-science compatible gating geometry, that is, the presence of the sample surface of two galvanically isolated regions, yet extremely close to each other, such that one region can act as a gate on objects deposited on top of the other. This project has been delayed with respect to the initial timeline because (i) ESR2 was hired 8 months after project start and (ii) we have recently upgraded our low-temperature combined AFM-STM setup as to integrate an ultra-high vacuum chamber for in situ surface and tip preparation. This new setup is now completed and close to be up and running. The current project status is as follows:

- *Fabrication of a local gating geometry*: we now routinely nanofabricate substrates entirely covered by two macroscopic galvanically isolated regions, separated by less than 50 nm (Fig. 1) over millimeter distances. Leakage currents as low as 5 μA at 1 Volt potential differences are achieved. This is already acceptable for working at 4 K, but does produce excessive dissipation for working at 100 mK. Strategies for further improvement will be explored in the coming weeks.
- *Tunneling spectroscopies on nanoparticles*: we are able to deposit and image 15-nm diameter gold nanoparticles on the above substrates (Fig. 1). So far, low-temperature tunneling spectroscopies have suffered from tip and sample contaminations, which render the reproducibility of the results insufficient. This will be strongly improved owing to the in situ surface preparation capabilities, which are close to being implemented.
- *Ultra-high vacuum surface preparation chamber coupled to the dilution refrigerated STM*: We have recently installed a new UHV surface preparation chamber with the following features: pressure = $2\text{E}-10$ mbar, ion gun, e-beam evaporator, sample annealing to 1450 K, sample cooling to 100 K, in situ transfer to dilution-refrigerated STM. The chamber is up and running. Integration of the cryogenic STM will be completed by March 2020.

Figure 1 : Top left images: meander line separating the two galvanically isolated metallic surfaces. Nanoparticles are seen as white spots. Top right: tunneling spectroscopy indicating a possible Coulomb gap. Bottom: new UHV chamber. The cryostat is on the right side of the setup.